

ORGANIZATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE FINANCIAL SITUATION OF RAILWAY TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES

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Annotation. This article explores the methodological aspects of improving the analysis of the financial condition of economic entities on the example of railway transport enterprises.

The article analyzes the factors influencing the financial situation, using the example of passenger transportation, provides scientific proposals and practical recommendations necessary for making effective management decisions.

Key words: financial condition, financial result, cost of products, works and services, period expenses, financial stability.

Since the creation of railway transport in our country, it has been working effectively in collaboration with enterprises in the real sector of the economy. In particular, an increase in the share of industrial production on the railway network, the development of construction and contracting activities in underground and surface metro systems, and an increase in the volume of passenger and freight traffic place new demands on services in this area.

One of the main and important strategic objectives of the network is to ensure high-quality performance of freight and passenger transportation based on modern requirements in order to meet the needs of the economy.

The joint stock company “O‘ztemiryulyulovchi”, which is the object of our research, has the status of a legal entity and carries out its activities in accordance with the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the charter of the company. The society consists of 7 regional branches. There are also other branches of the joint-stock company serving passenger transportation:

Departments of technical and technological preparation of passenger trains for the trip;

Branches of “Tashkent Central Stations”;

Railway Agency;

Agency of Tourism, Advertising and Marketing Research;

Department of passenger trains and passenger services.

The financial condition of an enterprise is a set of indicators that reflect its ability to repay a debt obligation. It is characterized by the provision of financial

resources necessary for the normal functioning of the enterprise, their appropriate placement and effective use, financial relationships with other legal entities and individuals, solvency and financial stability.

Indicators of economic efficiency of the enterprise “On measures to further improve the system for assessing the efficiency of the executive body of state enterprises” of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 9, 2020 No. 775 forecast of the main indicators necessary for efficiency indicators” was developed for 2022.

International UN experts divide financial stability ratios into five categories:
independence coefficient;
share of credit funds;
ratio of own and borrowed funds;
amount of accounts receivable;

One of the important indicators of financial stability, recommended by UN international experts, are liquidity indicators, which consist of the following ratios: absolute liquidity ratio; intermediate coverage ratio; overall coverage ratio; inventory liquidity ratio; liquidity of assets.

In accordance with Appendix 2 of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1013 dated December 14, 2018 “On measures to radically improve the system of financial rehabilitation of enterprises with state participation” “Regulation on the procedure for providing information for analyzing the financial and economic condition of enterprises with state participation” and for analysis of the financial condition of enterprises in need of financial recovery, the following key indicators (criteria) are used: solvency or coverage ratio; coefficient of provision with own working capital; ratio of return on assets and costs.

There are four types of financial stability:

- first – absolute stability of financial condition;
- second – normal stability of financial condition, which guarantees the solvency of the enterprise;
- third – an unstable financial condition associated with a violation of solvency, while maintaining the possibility of restoring balance by replenishing sources of own funds and attracting borrowed funds;
- fourth - a financial crisis, close to bankruptcy, when cash, short-term securities and receivables of the enterprise do not cover accounts payable and overdue loans.

It is also recommended to use the following additional indicators: the ratio of own and short-term borrowed funds; capacity utilization rate; depreciation rate for fixed assets.

All relative indicators of financial stability can be divided into two groups:

The first group is indicators that determine the state of working capital:

- equity ratio;
- coefficient of provision of material reserves with own working capital;
- coefficient of maneuverability of own funds.

The second group is indicators characterizing the degree of financial independence:

- autonomy coefficient;
- ratio of equity and borrowed funds.

Liquidity indicators are used to assess the ability of the enterprise at the moment, but also in case of emergency.

Liquidity and solvency are not identical to each other.

Solvency means that an enterprise has cash and cash equivalents sufficient to pay accounts payable that require immediate repayment.

The main signs of solvency are: a) the presence of sufficient funds in the current account; b) absence of overdue accounts payable. And, liquidity ratios can characterize the financial situation as satisfactory, however, in essence, this assessment may be erroneous if in current assets a significant proportion falls on illiquid assets and overdue receivables.

The dynamics of indicators reflecting the main activities of the joint-stock company were analyzed during the research process. When analyzing passenger turnover, 2021 showed an overall high result

(2571.1 passengers/km). In 2022, there was an increase in domestic local transportation by 193.6% compared to 2021. The most effective result in the international direction (15.4) was in 2020. If we analyze the number of passengers transported, the most effective result (5968.2) was recorded in 2021 compared to the total figure for the years. In 2021, compared to other years, an effective result was recorded on the local, international and suburban route (3127 thousand people). The negative result for 2022 (10.7 million roads/km) was ensured by the international route. The number of passengers transported in 2021 increased by 188.6% compared to 2020. Domestically, we see that 2021 has been a productive year.

The results of the analysis of indicators characterizing the financial position of the joint-stock company based on the information from the "Statement of

Financial Results (Form 2)” show that the net income from sales of products (goods, works, services) at the end of 2022 is 435,245,614 thousand soums, compared to the beginning of the year 127, an increase of 0 percent.

The cost of products sold (goods, works, services) at the beginning of the year amounted to 263,238,056 thousand soums, and at the end of the reporting year this figure increased to 299,887,477 thousand soums. One of the important points that should be noted is that the weight of product costs in sales income at the beginning of the year was 76.7%, and by the end of the year this figure decreased to 68.9%. up to 86,553,552 thousand soums or 123.5% requires optimization of administrative, management and sales costs.

We see that income from the financial activities of the joint-stock company did not have a significant weight, amounted to 2,115,029 thousand soums at the end of the year and decreased by 89.6% (20,327,980 thousand soums) compared to the beginning of the year. . Therefore, one of the important tasks of the company in this regard is to place its shares in sectors that generate income on the stock market, diversify the portfolio of shares and take measures to increase the receipt of dividends from them.

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